

SENSING OF RESIN FLOW AND CURE IN CONTINUOUS FIBER ADDITIVE MANUFACTURING

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ABSTRACT

This research represents a comprehensive approach to monitoring resin flow and cure in static condition and during continuous fiber additive manufacturing (CFAM), focusing on advanced sensing technologies and their integration into the manufacturing setup. In-situ process monitoring like sensing real time resin flow and cure in CFAM are critically important factors that significantly influence the final mechanical properties, dimensional accuracy, and quality of the composite parts. In this study, 12K carbon fiber tow has been used as the precursor and been investigated as a sensor itself to monitor the resin flow and cure during composite manufacturing for automotive application. The sensitivity of carbon fiber was measured in terms of electrical resistance change in-situ by utilizing a 4-wire electrical resistance measurement system. To better understand the structural geometry and sensing property, the electrical resistance change was measured for single filament, multiple filaments and whole bundle of 12K carbon fiber tow during resin infusion and curing. For further sensitivity analysis, 12K carbon fiber tow was coated with carbon nanotube (CNT) by electrophoretic deposition (EPD). CNT has been an instrumental material for sensing because of its excellent electrical, thermal and mechanical properties. CNT network on carbon fiber was confirmed by microscopic analysis. For dynamic process sensing, a customized set-up has been developed to achieve real-time process monitoring by integrating 4-wire resistance measurement system into the set-up without embedding any external sensor.

1 INTRODUCTION

Continuous fiber additive manufacturing (CFAM) is a cutting-edge technology with significant implications across various industries especially in composite manufacturing for high performance applications like automotive, aerospace, marine, medical devices, sports and many more. The emergence of this technology has highlighted a need for real-time sensing during the manufacturing process. Online process monitoring during CFAM is crucial for maintaining the quality and integrity of produced parts. It allows for real-time detection of defects and anomalies during on-line production. This ensures that any deviations from the desired parameters can be identified and corrected immediately, preventing the production of faulty parts and ensuring consistent product quality. By providing real-time data and enabling immediate adjustments, online monitoring helps in detecting and correcting defects such as voids, delamination, and misalignments early in the process, thereby minimizing material waste and rework costs. Furthermore, it supports the collection of detailed process data, facilitating the optimization of manufacturing parameters and enhancing overall efficiency.

Studies have highlighted the importance of such monitoring systems in improving process reliability and product performance, ultimately contributing to the advancement and competitiveness of CFAM technologies^{1,2}. The adoption of online process monitoring is also essential for meeting stringent regulatory requirements and industry standards, ultimately driving innovation and maintaining a competitive edge in the market^{3,4}.

Carbon nanotube (CNT) is an instrumental material in nano-engineering. CNT based sensors are significant due to their exceptional properties, such as high surface area, excellent electrical conductivity, mechanical strength, and chemical stability, which make them highly sensitive and responsive to various stimuli, including liquid, gases, biomolecules, and physical forces⁵⁻⁸. These sensors are motivated by the need for ultra-sensitive, rapid, and reliable detection systems in fields like composite manufacturing, environmental & structural health monitoring, healthcare, and industrial safety. The conductive CNTs can be deposited onto conventional fibers to create composites making the composites piezoresistive. Consequently, the resistance changes in case any mechanical or structural deformations of composites. Thus, CNT composites allow them to be used in a variety of sensing functions with higher sensitivity than conventional composites. Furthermore, the flexibility and compatibility of CNT with various substrates enable the development of versatile and wearable sensor devices. Research has demonstrated that CNT-based sensors can outperform traditional sensors in terms of sensitivity, response time, and durability, driving their adoption in cutting-edge applications⁹⁻¹¹.

The advancement of continuous carbon fiber additive manufacturing has revolutionized the production of high-strength, lightweight composite materials, essential for industries such as aerospace, automotive, and defense. However, the lack of effective online process monitoring poses significant challenges in ensuring the consistency, quality, and reliability of the manufactured parts. The reported research works on the sensing properties of carbon fiber have been very limited compared to its well-documented mechanical and structural benefits. While carbon fiber is renowned for its high strength-to-weight ratio and durability, its potential as a sensor material remains underexplored. Very few studies reported the process monitoring of carbon fiber composite in static condition utilizing traditional sensors like dielectric sensor, optical sensor or by using camera^{12,13}. The lack of comprehensive studies in this area suggests a need for further investigation to fully harness carbon fiber's capabilities in advanced sensing technologies. To the best of our knowledge, no research has been reported on the in-situ process monitoring of dynamic carbon fiber additive manufacturing process so far. Therefore, this research aims to address this gap by exploring and implementing advanced sensing and data analysis techniques to enhance the accuracy, efficiency, and reliability of carbon fiber AM processes without utilizing any embedded sensor. By providing real-time data on parameters such as resin flow, temperature, and curing kinetics, it is possible to detect and correct process deviations promptly. This real-time adjustment capability will reduce the occurrence of defects, such as voids and incomplete curing, leading to enhanced mechanical properties and overall performance of the carbon fiber composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and Methods

Polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based 12K continuous carbon fiber tow (filament diameter-5.2 microns) was sourced from Hexcel Corporation. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT; CM-95, Hanwha Nanotech, South Korea) were mixed into ultra-pure water at a concentration of 1g/L in a 2-liter flask. The flask was then placed into a cooling bath maintained at 5°C and the mixture was sonicated by Ozone gas for 10 hours. After the oxidation step, 2 grams of polyethyleneimine (PEI) was added into the ozone-treated dispersion followed by sonication for an additional 4 hours. To protonate the CNT surface by the amine groups of PEI, the pH of the dispersion was adjusted to 5.8 using glacial acetic acid (Sigma-Aldrich, USA). The functionalized CNTs remained well dispersed for long period of time due to repulsion among themselves being positively charged by PEI treatment. Commercially available

Fiberglast 4600 resin and Fiberglast 4690 curing agent are used as the epoxy system in this study. The resin and hardener were mixed in 5:1 ratio for infusion.

2.2 Electrophoretic Deposition

Electrophoretic deposition (EPD) is a versatile processing technique for coating without the requirement of binders. For EPD, the samples are fixed across an electrode and another electrode is clamped in a way that both electrodes remain 1 cm apart from each other as shown on Figure 1a. In EPD, charged colloidal particles dispersed or suspended in a liquid medium are attracted and deposited onto an electrically conductive substrate with opposite charges under an electric field (Figure 1b). To characterize the morphology of uncoated and CNT coated carbon fiber tow, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analysis was done.

Figure 1: Sample preparation for EPD (a) and EPD setup (b).

2.3 CNT-Based Sensing

CNT based sensing leverages the unique electrical, mechanical, and chemical properties of CNTs to create highly sensitive and responsive sensors for various applications. Over the last two decades, Professor Dr. Erik T Thostenson and his group have been investigating a CNT-based in situ sensing approach for detecting and quantifying various parameters in structural health monitoring, composite manufacturing and human health monitoring¹⁴⁻¹⁸. With many other developments, CNT based fabric sensors to monitor the resin flow and its position were developed, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2: CNT based sensor developed for process sensing during composites manufacturing¹⁷.

2.4 Measurement of Electrical Sensitivity of Carbon Fiber

Single filament, multiple filaments, and whole tow of IM7 12K carbon fiber were tested to measure their electrical response while infusing resin at elevated temperatures. As shown in Figure 3, samples were placed on a glass slide and electrodes were attached to samples by silver epoxy. After specimen preparation, the glass slides were placed on a hot plate. Then the electrical response of samples was measured by 4-wire electrical resistance measurement system dropping the resin from top in the middle of the specimens.

Figure 3: Experimental setup for resistance changes measurement of single filament (a), multiple filaments (b), whole tow (c) of carbon fibers.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Morphological Analysis

As shown in Figure 4a, the uncoated fiber exhibits a smooth and clean surface, characteristic of pristine carbon fibers. In contrast, Figure 4b reveals a rough and textured surface morphology resulting from the deposition of CNTs onto the fiber surface. The CNT coating, applied via EPD, forms a uniform and dense network over the fiber, enhancing its surface area and potentially improving interfacial bonding and electrical conductivity. This morphological transformation confirms successful CNT deposition and highlights the effectiveness of EPD as a surface treatment technique.

Figure 4: SEM image of uncoated (a) and CNT coated carbon fiber (b).

3.2 Thermal Impact on the Sensing Properties of Carbon Fiber

Single filaments were extracted from IM7 12K Carbon fiber tow to analyze their sensing property at different temperature gradients. To measure the electrical sensitivity, all samples were kept inside the desiccator for 24 hours to make the samples moisture free prior to the experiment. Then samples were placed on a glass slide and electrodes were attached to the samples by silver epoxy. The sensitivity of the samples was tested in terms of electrical resistance change% as a function of time and temperature. The test was performed to determine the resistance change by increasing the temperature without any interval from room temperature to 100°C and then lowered the temperature to room temperature as shown in Figure 5a. It was observed that as temperature increases, the resistance change decreases up to 2.5%. Notably, as temperature was decreased to room temperature the resistance change% exhibited the opposite trend showing hysteresis loop as demonstrated in Figure 5b.

Figure 5: Electrical resistance change of single carbon fiber filament upon heating (a) and hysteresis behavior upon cooling (b).

3.3 Cure Kinetics of Fibreglast 4600/4690 Resin

The epoxy system used in this research is commercially available Fibreglast 4600, a low viscosity system that allows it to penetrate into the reinforcing materials easily, producing less void making it an ideal selection for quality composite manufacturing. To examine the cure kinetics of the Fibreglast 4600 epoxy resin, it was mixed with Fibreglast 4690 hardener in the ratio of 5:1 by wt%. A NETZSCH DSC214 Polyma was used to generate the kinetics model of Fibreglast 4600. A set of the aluminum crucibles and lids were weighed before and after being filled up with a well-mixed resin droplet to measure the weight of the resin. Before crimping the Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) pans, a small hole on the lid was punched with a needle to make sure that the pressure difference inside and outside of the pan was minimized. Weighed samples (of 8 mg) were crimped in an aluminum crucible and heated up to 250°C under inert nitrogen at different ramping rates as 2°C/min, 5°C/min and 10°C/min.

3.4 Model-based Analysis

Model-based cure kinetics was developed using commercially available Kinetics NEO software. This model helps to predict the resin system's cure behavior under a certain temperature program. The cure kinetics of Fibreglast 4600/4690 resin system can be characterized by the following general equation:

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = Aa^n \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) + Bb^n \exp\left(\frac{-E_a}{RT}\right) \quad (1)$$

Where α is conversion rate, A and B are pre-exponential factor, a, b are arbitrary kinetic models, n is the reaction order, E_a is the activation energy, R is the universal gas constant and T is the absolute

temperature. Specific values for the parameters are shown in Table 1. Figure 6 shows the DSC thermograms and cure conversion of Fibreglast 4600 mixed with Fibreglast 4690 at a heating rate of 2°C/min, 5°C/min and 10 °C/min. The exothermic peak of each graph shifted to a higher temperature exhibiting faster curing at lower ramping rate. Two peaks of each DSC curve represent two-steps (A→B→C) reaction governed by Equation 1. The DSC graphs and the conversion graphs represent well compatibility between model and experimental data.

Figure 6: DSC analysis (a) and cure conversion (b) showing model fitting with experimental data.

Table 1: Reaction parameters for cure kinetics model of Fibreglast 4600/4690 resin system

Reaction Step	Ea (kJ/mol)	Log(A)	Log(B)	Reaction Order (n)
A→B	56.357	5.264	-	1.048
B→C	82.074	-	8.389	2.415

3.4 Correlation with Kinetics and *in situ* Sensing

The developed cure kinetics model allowed time-temperature history analysis to predict the degree of cure of Fibreglast resin. As shown in Figure 7a, according to model it was observed that almost 90% curing of the resin system is done within 3.5 minutes and 20 minutes approximately at 150°C and 90°C respectively which well aligned with the *in-situ* experimental sensing response as shown in Figure 7b. A 4-probe electrical resistance measurement system was employed to monitor the real time resin flow and curing after dropping the resin on the stationary samples of 12K carbon fiber tow. Experiments were done at 150°C and 90°C. The results showed that up to ~35% resistance change occurs during resin infusion and the electrical resistance change curve shows flattening within 3.5 minutes since the resin infusion point at 150°C. Model prediction and sensor response were also studied at lower temperature. In case of curing at 90°C, both model and experimental results showed that it takes more than 20 minutes for 90% curing of the resin system. In both cases, the electrical resistance of the carbon fiber tow increases right after resin infusion because of the infiltration of electrically non-conductive epoxy resin into the carbon fiber bundles and the morphological disorientation of the conductive network of bundles due to resin flow. The slight decrease in resistance change is observed before flattening the resistance change curve during curing at both 150°C and 90°C as demonstrated in Figure 7b which could be due to volumetric shrinkage of the polymer matrix and gradual compression of the conductive fiber network during curing progression.

Figure 7: Cure prediction by the kinetics model (a) and *in-situ* sensing response of resin flow and curing at 150°C and 90°C.

3.5 Online Process Monitoring of Continuous Additive Manufacturing

A customized setup was developed in collaboration for resin impregnation and on-line monitoring in dynamic system. Figure 8a represents the schematic of basic setup for dynamic process and the detailed features of resin impregnation bath is shown in Figure 8b. Details B and C illustrate the fiber tow manipulation as it passes between the metallic pins. The lateral offset ensures that the fiber tow is in continuous contact with metal pins. Metallic pins are connected to a data acquisition system for *in-situ* process monitoring by a 4-wire electrical resistance measurement system.

Figure 8: Basic setup for dynamic process monitoring (a) and the detailed features of resin impregnation bath (b).

3.6 On-line Process Sensing

For dynamic process monitoring, electrodes were connected to metallic pins which are in direct contact with carbon fiber tow at both ends of resin impregnation bath. As demonstrated in Figure 9, the resistance change before the resin bath was negative which may be because of decreasing the inter filament distance during pulling and change in contact resistance. On the other hand, higher resistance change was observed after the resin bath upon pulling resin impregnated tow because of resin infusion into the inter filament gaps of the tow. Resistance change again came down and became stable after

stopping pulling the tow. Thus in-situ resistance change measurement system showed promising results for online monitoring of resin infusion in a dynamic setup. Due to various tension variations in the dynamic setup and highly anisotropic nature of carbon fiber tow, the noise in sensitivity measurement was observed which could be minimized by the modification of dynamic setup and electrical reconfiguration.

Figure 9: *In situ* resin infusion monitoring in a dynamic setup before and after the resin bath.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study demonstrates a comprehensive, non-invasive approach for real-time monitoring of resin flow and cure during static and continuous fiber additive manufacturing using the inherent electrical properties of 12K carbon fiber tow. The curing behavior of the Fiberglast 4600/4690 resin system was thoroughly investigated and validated using both a kinetics model and experimental data. The experimental setup, employing the 4-wire method for electrical resistance measurements, enabled accurate monitoring of resin infusion and curing in real time. This combined approach provided a robust validation of the kinetics model, demonstrating a strong correlation between predicted and observed curing behavior. These findings underscore the potential of using electrical resistance measurements as a reliable, non-invasive method for real-time monitoring and control of resin curing processes, which could enhance manufacturing consistency and quality assurance in advanced composite applications. Further modifications of dynamic setup and electrode reconfiguration can be done in future work for the precise process monitoring in CFAM.

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